

Proceedings of AfriWUIFire Workshop

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2025 March

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Acknowledgements

This workshop was organized as a part of AfriWUIFire project activity. This workshop was supported by JST Strategic International Collaborative Research Program (SICORP) Grant Number JPMJS23A3, Japan.

Preface

The AfriWUIFire workshop was held in Ookayama Campus, Institute of Science Tokyo and in Zoom on February 20th 2025. More than 60 people were registered for this workshop, mostly from Japan, South Africa, and Botswana. Due to requests, we publish presentation slides as proceedings of AfriWUIFire workshop.

Introduction

Fire Safe African Homes in the Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Project (AfriWUIFire), under the Africa-Japan Collaborative Research (AJ-CORE), funded jointly by Japan Science and Technology Agency (Japan), National Research Foundation (South Africa) and Department of Research, Science and Technology (Botswana), aims to improve fire safety in Africa through the investigation on Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) fire risk by firebrand ignition in Southern Africa. This project started from April 2023. As a conclusion of project's first year, AfriWUIFire workshop provides overall project information as well as progress.

Members of AfriWUIFire Team

Co-PIs:

Top (Left to Right): Sayaka Suzuki (Institute of Science Tokyo), Samuel L. Manzello (Tohoku U) Rejoice Tsheko (Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources)
Bottom (Left to Right): Doug Harebottle (Sol Plaatje U) Natalia Flores-Quiroz Richard Walls (Stellenbosch U)

Members:

Guy Godiraone Yuyi (BUAN)

Ednah Kgosiesele (BUAN)

Patricia Maswibilili (BUAN)

Reita Kameyama (Science Tokyo)

Yuki Hara (Science Tokyo)

Miss Hasimawaty Binti Mat Kiah (PostDoc at Stellenbosch U.)

Emile van Zyl (Master student at Stellenbosch U.)

Phetole Ramatsoma (PostDoc at Sol Plaatje U.)

Final Agenda

Japan Time	Africa Time	Title	Speaker
15:00-15:15	8:00-8:15	Welcome	Suzuki (Science Tokyo)
15:15-15:45	8:15-8:45	Overview of AfriWUIFire	Suzuki (Science Tokyo) Walls (SU)
15:45-16:05	8:45-9:05	Structure vulnerability study in SA	Hasimawaty and Flores-Quiroz (SU)
16:05-16:25	9:05-9:25	Structure vulnerability study in Botswana	Yuyi and Tsheko (BUAN)
16:25-16:55	9:25-9:55	Vegetation study -selection process for both SA and Botswana	Van Zyl and Flores-Quiroz (SU) Yuyi and Tsheko (BUAN)
16:55-17:15	9:55-10:15	Regulation in Africa: Case of Botswana and South Africa	Phetole Ramatsoma (SPU)
17:15-17:35	10:15-10:35	Progress to Develop Global Test Methods for Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fires	Manzello (Tohoku U)
17:35-17:55	10:35-10:55	Discussion	All
17:55-18:00	10:55-11:00	Closing & Group Picture	All

Appendix Presentation Slides

Long Term Africa-Japan Research and Innovation Partnership

AfriWUIFire: Fire safe African homes on the Wildland Urban Interface - Workshop

Agenda

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Welcome to

- Teams:
 - Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources (BUAN)
 - Tohoku University (Japan)
 - Institute of Science Tokyo (Japan)
 - Sol Plaatje University (South Africa)
 - Stellenbosch University (South Africa)
- Delegates associated with the AJ-Core (Japan / SA / Botswana)
- Industry partners
- Delegates from various countries and industries

Welcome

To Online participants:

- Please mute yourself during the presentation
- If you have questions, please use the “raise hands” button or write them in chat
 - If you use the “raise hands” button, we will ask you to speak, then unmute yourself and ask questions
 - If you write questions or comments in chat, you or we can read that questions
 - We may not have enough time after each presentation, we can come back to your questions during Discussion at the end

Welcome

About the AJ-CORE Program

- Africa-Japan Collaborative Research is a multilateral research framework connecting three (or more) countries: Japan (supported by JST), South Africa (supported by NRF) and at least one African country (Science Granting Councils Initiative African countries).
- Call is for “Environmental Science”
- AfriWUIFire is one of 3rd call projects

Welcome

AJ-CORE Workshop at Maun, 2024 April

Overview of AfriWUIFire

The objectives of the project are to:

- Characterize typical structures in South Africa and Botswana, including construction materials, and construction typologies.
- Identify typical vegetation in South Africa and Botswana.
- Develop fire experiments to understand the impact of firebrands on different construction features.
- Provide scientifically based inputs to develop guidelines for improving fire resilience in communities located in WUI areas.
- Look into policy and intervention in order to improve our response, policy, organisations, and codes.

Overview of AfriWUIFire

- Fire engineering and sciences

- Policy research

- Land usage / GIS

Overview of AfriWUIFire

- Progress to date:
 - Kick-off meeting
 - Characterisation of homes in SA and Botswana.
 - International training visit
 - Burner was designed
 - The visit is featured in Tohoku U's news https://www.tohoku.ac.jp/en/news/university_news/japanese_and_african_researchers_join_forces_to_tackle_wildfire_threats.html
 - Reports being developed.
 - Preliminary testing
 - Development of teams and capacity enhancement
 - Appointing of students and postdocs.

Fire safe African homes on the wildland urban interface (AfriWUIFire)

1. Project Overview
This poster summarizes work being conducted to protect homes in sub-Saharan Africa on the Wildland Urban Interface (WUI). The objectives of the project are to:
1. Characterize typical structures in South Africa and Botswana, including construction materials, and construction typologies.
2. Identify typical vegetation in South Africa and Botswana.
3. Develop fire experiments to understand the impact of freboards on different construction features.
4. Provide scientifically based inputs to develop guidelines for improving the resistance in communities located in WUI areas.
5. Look into policy and intervention in order to improve our responses, policy, organisations, and codes.
This poster focuses on points 1 and 2, considering construction materials and typical typologies, along with important vegetative species.

2. Analysis of homes
Around 240 homes across South Africa and 225 homes in Botswana have been analyzed in terms of their architectural features and how these impact ignition due to ember attack during WUI fires. Some provisional findings include:
• High variability in home features from area to area.
• Newer areas tend to be large estates with more homogenous features.
• Features such as solar panels on roofs, complex roof shapes, and chimneys correlate more strongly with higher income homes.
• Due to local climatic conditions, there are fewer roof ventilation features than found in many northern hemisphere homes.
• Identification of indigenous home types in rural areas, often incorporating combustibles materials.

3. Experimental results
This work was supported by JST Strategic International Collaborative Research Program (SCORP), Grant Number PMHSC23A3, Japan.

4. Acknowledgements
The next phase of the work will focus on testing various species of local plants to understand firebrand generation. The data will be utilized to decide the characteristics of freboards for next series of experiments. This will be followed by the characterization of home susceptibility to firebrand attack.

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News

Japanese and African Researchers Join Forces to Tackle Wildfire Threats

2025-01-24 University News

In February, researchers from South Africa and Botswana will visit Japan to undergo training on combustion research. The training is part of a project supported by a Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST) program, aimed at improving the resilience of local communities against wildfires in southern Africa, particularly focusing on firebrand showers.

Firebrand Showers
The fires that raged across Los Angeles this January brought into sharp focus the dangers wildfires pose to urban areas. Scientists dub these fire wildland urban interface (WUI) fires, where wildfires encroach into urban spaces, leaving behind destruction reminiscent of an apocalyptic movie. Similar catastrophes seen in Greece, Maui and Canada show that the prevalence of WUI fires is on the rise.

Recent News

2025-01-27
Category: Recruitment Notice: Professor

2025-01-24
University News
Japanese and African Researchers Join Forces to Tackle Wildfire Threats

2025-01-22
Category: Recruitment Notice: Associate Professor

SAICE Fire Engineering Division lecture

The LA wildfires: Could they happen in South Africa?

18 February 2025

The devastating wildfires in Los Angeles have destroyed thousands of homes, caused many fatalities and billions of dollars worth of damage. Could similar events happen in the future in South Africa, and what can we do to prepare for them? Considering that in 2017 around 1000 homes were burnt down in Knyana, coupled with drought conditions and growing populations, we could see large loss events in SA, even if not on the same magnitude of LA.

The talk will also consider how to improve the wildfire resistance of homes along with case studies from SA.

Dr. Natalia Flores Quiroz
Researcher, Stellenbosch University

Patrick Ryan
Managing Director, Wildfire Management

DATE: 18 February 2025
TIME: 15:00
Click on the link provided to register to attend the event that will be held in MS Teams.
To be CPD Accredited

Dr. Natalia Flores Quiroz is a researcher with 12 years experience in fire safety engineering. Her work focuses on wildland-urban interface (WUI) fires and fire safety in low-income settlements. She contributed to the reconstruction of the 2017 Knyana fires and is collaborating on projects addressing WUI fire risks in diverse settings, including biodiversity conservation, infrastructure protection and fuel management.

Patrick Ryan's background in wildfire suppression began in 2011 as a volunteer wildland fire practitioner with the Volunteer Wildfire Services and his passion for wildfire management progressed to a career as a professional wildfire manager in the wildfire industry.

Email address: debbe@saice.org.za

SAICE

Project (Final) Outputs

- Fire safety guideline for homes located in the WUI.
- Webinars.
- Workshops with residents and decision makers from the community.
- Research papers.

Overview of AfriWUIFire

- Fire risk in Southern Africa
 - Various climatic regions.
 - Often dry, savannah-like areas.
 - Growing populations expanding into WUI areas.
 - Lack of fire service capacity.
 - Many groups involved.
- Western Cape has the strongest wildfire capacity and knowledge so a good place to launch from.

Greetings from Africa

1.3 billion people

54 countries

The Changing World

The number of people in extreme poverty – including projections to 2030

Extreme poverty is defined by the 'international poverty line' as living on less than \$1.90/day. This is measured by adjusting for price changes over time and for price differences between countries (PPP adjustment). From 2015 to 2030 the World Bank's projections are shown.

Our World
in Data

1.9 billion people lived in extreme poverty in 1990 (36% of the world population)

Data source: World Bank data from 1990 to 2015. The projections from 2015 to 2030 are published in the World Bank report *Poverty and Shared Prosperity 2018*.

This is a visualization from [OurWorldinData.org](https://ourworldindata.org), where you find data and research on how the world is changing.

Licensed under CC-BY by the author Max Roser.

<https://ourworldindata.org/extreme-poverty>

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Fig. 3. Number of homes/structures affected for each case study. In pink is the Kanonkop/Kynsna Heights/Paradise region, in blue the Belvidere area and in yellow the Kranshoek area. (Circles only represent location, not exact area studied). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Location of the origin of the three fires seen in 2017 in Knysna-Plettenberg Bay Area, South Africa and the weather stations. (Burn scar provided courtesy of the CSIR and CapeNature). Yellow circles show location of weather stations used in this work. (Circles only represent estimated origin location). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Analysis of the 2017 Knysna fires disaster with emphasis on fire spread, home losses and the influence of vegetation and weather conditions: A South African case study

Natalia Flores Quiroz^{a,*}, Lesley Gibson^{a,b}, Willem Stefaan Conrardie^c, Patrick Ryan^d, Ryan Heydenrych^d, Ashton Moran^a, Armandt van Straten^a, Richard Walls^a

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ARTICLE INFO

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 Home survivability
 Wildland urban interface (WUI)
 Fire spread
 GIS

ABSTRACT

Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) fires are becoming more common globally. However, most research has been focused on developed regions such as North America and Australia, exposing a lack of geographical diversity in the field. This paper presents an analysis of South Africa's largest WUI fire disaster, in terms of the number of structures lost and the economic losses, the 2017 Knysna fires. The data used in this report is based on aerial reconnaissance conducted immediately after the event, a geo-located database identifying homes that were destroyed, satellite imagery and site visits. The analysis includes the fire spread mechanisms, firebreak efficiency, the influence of roof and wall types, vegetation, and weather conditions. The Canadian Fire Weather Index (FWI) values on the day of ignition were unprecedented in the 1979–2021 period, the culmination of a clear multi-decadal trend towards greater fire weather risk. Due to the combination of severe medium-term drought and extreme fire weather conditions homes up to 1 km inside the WUI were destroyed. The high wind speeds allowed the fire to cross natural and artificial barriers such as rivers and highways, allowing the ignition of several secondary fires due to ember attacks. Construction materials and fire exposure, which is influenced by the presence of vegetation, affected home survivability. Combustible materials (thatch and timber) typically made homes more susceptible to fire damage. It was found that in the areas where more structures were affected the vegetation were dense, highly flammable stands of alien invasive vegetation.

1. Introduction

Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) fires are becoming more common globally [1,2] due to, amongst other, population growth, economic reasons (rapidly increasing urban property prices), people wanting to live near natural areas, and changes in land use [3]. The growing number of houses constructed in high-risk areas, the increase in temperature and regional droughts due to climate change, and the build-up of available fuels have increased the fire related risk [4–6]. The investigation of real fires is essential to learn from past incidents about fire spread mechanisms, firefighting activities, home survivability and social-economic impacts [7]. Table 1 presents some of recent WUI fire incidents in various countries and their impacts.

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Overview of AfriWUIFire

Fig. 12. Fire jumps. (a) Fire cross at the N2 [61]. (b) Fire cross at Rheenendal Road [82]. (c) Fire crossing the Harkerville Forest. The fire head is marked with the red arrow, the yellow arrows show spot fires that did not develop in low flammability vegetation, and the pink arrow depicts the location where the fire brands reached a pine plantation [61]. (d) Home destroyed by the fire (left bottom), on the other side of the road the homes were not affected [35]. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fire Spread Mechanism in Outdoor Fires

Direct Flame Contact

Thermal Radiation

Firebrands

Overview of AfriWUIFire

900 km (domain)

~8 km (grid cell)

1 km (domain)

~1 m (grid cell)

Regional

Landscape

Community

**Fuel
elements**

Combustion Community Critical

**W. Mell, S.L. Manzello, *et al.*,
Int. J. Wildland Fire, 2010**

Overview of AfriWUIFire

S.L. Manzello, et al., Progress in Energy and Combustion Science, 2020

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Suzuki, Naruse, and Manzello, *Fire Technology*, 2024, in press

Another parallel concept testing methodologies to allow buildings to produce less firebrands during fires

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Tree burn experiments (no wind)

First firebrand collection from a tree (Douglas-fir) under no wind was published in 2008.

Tree species	Mass of firebrands, m_{fb} (g)	Mass of firebrands/mass lost during burning (%)	Mass of firebrands/total tree mass (%)
Korean pine (4.0 m)	33 ± 15	2	0.28
Douglas-fir (2.6 m)	18 ± 4	0.45	0.15
Douglas-fir (5.2 m)	50 ± 5	0.2	0.08

Notes: Initial moisture content of all trees tested was similar.

Firebrand Yields from Conifer Trees
No wind
S.L. Manzello *et al.*, *Fire and Materials*, 2009

Korean Pine 4.0 m

Douglas-fir

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Tree burn experiments (with wind)

1.5 m Noble fir

No wind

3 m/s

Overview of AfriWUIFire

- 1.5 m Noble-fir (no wind)
- ◆ 1.5 m Noble-fir (3 m/s wind)
- ▲ 1.5 m Noble-fir (3 m/s)
(with needles)
- 2.6 m Douglas-fir (no wind)
- × 5.2 m Douglas-fir (no wind)
- △ 4.0 m Korean pine (no wind)

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Experiments with a firebrand generator

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Full-scale

Manzello, et al., *Fire Safety Journal*, 2011

Reduced-scale

Suzuki and Manzello, *Fire Technology*, 2021

To design structures to resist firebrand ignition, **one method** is to use standardized firebrand generator expose building components to a simulated firebrand attack to ascertain weak points and enable new designs to resist ignition

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Roof Assemblies

1. Firebrands accumulate in front of tile
2. Firebrands keep combusting and become smaller
3. Once firebrands become small enough, they penetrate tiles
4. Firebrands accumulate under tiles, leading to ignitions

Overview of AfriWUIFire

Roof Assemblies

- Firebrands collected under terracotta flat tiles
- Firebrands collected under concrete flat tiles
- ▲ Firebrands collected under Japanese-style tiles
- ◆ Firebrands collected under Japanese-style tiles (repeat)

Long Term Africa-Japan Research and Innovation Partnership

AfriWUIFire: Fire safe African homes on the Wildland Urban Interface - Workshop

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Introduction

How do homes burn?

Uninterrupted Vegetative fire

Structures are ignited by uninterrupted fire spread through continuous vegetative fuels up to the structure.

Interrupted Vegetative fire

Radiation or **fire brands** are involved either by igniting vegetation surrounding the structure or igniting the structure directly.

Structure to structure

Structures that are ignited by adjacent burning structures.

Introduction

- Firebrands are small, hot, carbonaceous particles that have the capability of setting additional fires.
- Firebrands can be generated from structures or from vegetation.
- Different type of vegetations produce different type of firebrands.
- In this project we will characterize the firebrands produced by vegetation typically found in SA and BW.

Introduction

- During an incident thousands of firebrands can rain down on a single structure and may ignite any exposed materials.
- Investigations of real fire events revealed firebrands were responsible for most structural ignitions.

Introduction

- The most susceptible components are roofs, windows frames and panes, eaves, and doors.
- Creating a defensible space around the structures has proven to be extremely important.

Methodology

- A stratified random sampling technique was used to select sample points within the high-income, middle income and low-income/informal/rural areas.
- Google Earth, Google street view and ArcGisSurvey123 tool were used in SA and BW.
- Field visits were also conducted in BW.
- A total of 565 structures were surveyed.
- Features such as building materials, roof characteristics, and defensible space were captured.

Structure vulnerability study results

General characteristics

Defensible space

Roof characteristics

Structure vulnerability study in SA

High income

Low income

Middle income

Structure vulnerability study in SA

High income

Low income

Middle income

Structure vulnerability study in SA

High income

Low income

Middle income

Structure vulnerability study in BW

High Income

Structure vulnerability study in BW

Middle Income

Low Income

Rural

Informal

Agenda

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Vegetation study - Methodology

Survey (<https://forms.gle/ScfkzPKZPG4aiyuD7>)

First, we'd like to ask you about trees/vegetations in wildland fires. There are 6 questions (7 if including your country choice).

Which country are you going answer? *

選択

In your opinion, what kind of trees **burn well** in wildland fires in the country you selected above? We'd appreciate as much detail (Latin names etc.) as possible if you can. (if you don't know, you can write "you don't know") *

回答を入力

Why do you think so? *

- based on my experience
- information from book, web, radio
- based on my research
- その他: _____

In your opinion, what kind of trees/vegetations **produce firebrands/embers/brands** in wildland fires in the country you selected above? We'd appreciate as much detail (Latin names etc.) as possible if you can. (if you don't know, you can write "you don't know") *

回答を入力

Why do you think so? *

- based on my experience
- information from book, web, radio
- based on my research
- その他: _____

⚠ この質問は必須です

Vegetation study for SA

Overview of South African vegetation

(Approximated map illustration)

Western Cape – Research area:

- Fynbos (*Predominantly*)
- Karoo

Vegetation study for SA

What kind of trees burn well in Wildland Fires?

- Pines
- Eucalyptus
- Acacia

What kind of trees or vegetation produces Firebrands or Embers in Wildland Fires?

- Fynbos (Protea)
- Pines
- Acacia
- Eucalyptus

Vegetation study for SA

Fynbos ‘in short’:

- “Fine-bush” or “fine-leaved plants”
- ~80% of the Cape floral kingdom
- more than 8,500 fynbos species

Fynbos and Fire:

- Fire plays critical role in survival of the species, some plants require the heat for their seeds to germinate
- Should burn between 6 and 45 years of age in order to sustain its plant species

Vegetation study for SA

Fynbos Biome

Fynbos vegetation types

- Agulhas Limestone Fynbos
- Agulhas Sand Fynbos
- Albertinia Sand Fynbos
- Algoa Sandstone Fynbos
- Atlantis Sand Fynbos
- Baviaanskloof Shale Renosterveld
- Blombos Strandveld
- Bokkeveld Sandstone Fynbos
- Boland Granite Fynbos
- Breede Alluvium Fynbos
- Breede Alluvium Renosterveld
- Breede Quartzite Fynbos
- Breede Sand Fynbos
- Breede Shale Fynbos
- Breede Shale Renosterveld
- Canca Limestone Fynbos
- Cape Flats Dune Strandveld
- Cape Flats Sand Fynbos
- Cape Winelands Shale Fynbos
- Cederberg Sandstone Fynbos
- Central Coastal Shale Band Vegetation
- Central Inland Shale Band Vegetation
- Central Mountain Shale Renosterveld
- Central Ruens Shale Renosterveld
- Ceres Shale Renosterveld
- Citrusdal Shale Renosterveld
- De Hoop Limestone Fynbos
- Eastern Coastal Shale Band Vegetation
- Eastern Inland Shale Band Vegetation
- Eastern Ruens Shale Renosterveld
- Elgin Shale Fynbos
- Elim Ferricrete Fynbos
- Garden Route Granite Fynbos
- Garden Route Shale Fynbos
- Graafwater Sandstone Fynbos
- Greyton Shale Fynbos
- Groot Brak Dune Strandveld
- Grootrivier Quartzite Fynbos
- Hangklip Sand Fynbos
- Hantam Plateau Dolerite Renosterveld

Fynbos Biome

- Hawequas Sandstone Fynbos
- Hopefield Sand Fynbos
- Humansdorp Shale Renosterveld
- Kamiesberg Granite Fynbos
- Kango Conglomerate Fynbos
- Kango Limestone Renosterveld
- Knysna Sand Fynbos
- Kogelberg Sandstone Fynbos
- Kouebokkeveld Alluvium Fynbos
- Kouebokkeveld Shale Fynbos
- Kouga Grassy Sandstone Fynbos
- Kouga Sandstone Fynbos
- Lambert's Bay Strandveld
- Langebaan Dune Strandveld
- Langkloof Shale Renosterveld
- Leipoldtville Sand Fynbos
- Loerie Conglomerate Fynbos
- Lourensford Alluvium Fynbos
- Matjiesfontein Quartzite Fynbos
- Matjiesfontein Shale Fynbos
- Matjiesfontein Shale Renosterveld
- Montagu Shale Fynbos
- Montagu Shale Renosterveld
- Mossel Bay Shale Renosterveld
- Namaqualand Granite Renosterveld
- Namaqualand Sand Fynbos
- Nardouw Sandstone Fynbos
- Nieuwoudtville Shale Renosterveld
- Nieuwoudtville-Roggeveld Dolerite Renosterveld
- North Hex Sandstone Fynbos
- North Kammanassie Sandstone Fynbos
- North Langeberg Sandstone Fynbos
- North Outeniqua Sandstone Fynbos
- North Rooiberg Sandstone Fynbos
- North Sonderend Sandstone Fynbos
- North Swartberg Sandstone Fynbos
- Northern Inland Shale Band Vegetation
- Olifants Sandstone Fynbos
- Overberg Dune Strandveld
- Overberg Sandstone Fynbos
- Peninsula Granite Fynbos
- Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos
- Peninsula Shale Fynbos
- Peninsula Shale Renosterveld
- Piketberg Sandstone Fynbos
- Potberg Ferricrete Fynbos
- Potberg Sandstone Fynbos
- Robertson Granite Fynbos
- Robertson Granite Renosterveld
- Roggeveld Shale Renosterveld
- Ruens Silcrete Renosterveld
- Saldanha Flats Strandveld
- Saldanha Granite Strandveld
- Saldanha Limestone Strandveld
- South Hex Sandstone Fynbos
- South Kammanassie Sandstone Fynbos
- South Langeberg Sandstone Fynbos
- South Outeniqua Sandstone Fynbos
- South Rooiberg Sandstone Fynbos
- South Sonderend Sandstone Fynbos
- South Swartberg Sandstone Fynbos
- Southern Cape Dune Fynbos
- Stinkfonteinberge Quartzite Fynbos
- Suurberg Quartzite Fynbos
- Suurberg Shale Fynbos
- Swartberg Altimontane Sandstone Fynbos
- Swartberg Shale Fynbos
- Swartberg Shale Renosterveld
- Swartland Alluvium Fynbos
- Swartland Alluvium Renosterveld
- Swartland Granite Renosterveld
- Swartland Shale Renosterveld
- Swartland Silcrete Renosterveld
- Swartruggens Quartzite Fynbos
- Swellendam Silcrete Fynbos
- Tsitsikamma Sandstone Fynbos
- Uniondale Shale Renosterveld
- Vanrhynsdorp Shale Renosterveld
- Western Altimontane Sandstone Fynbos
- Western Coastal Shale Band Vegetation
- Western Ruens Shale Renosterveld
- Winterhoek Sandstone Fynbos

Vegetation study for SA

Vegetation study for SA

Vegetation study for BW

BW –Vegetation Map highlighting “Acacia” (Vachellia and Senegalia) distribution

Vegetation study for BW

Tree species which burn well (Results)

- 9 acacia
- 2 Eucalyptus
- 5 Mophane - Colophospermum mopane (not within the study area)
- 2 Dichrostachys cinerea (moselesele) sickle bush
- 1 Fabaceae - includes Acacia and Senegalia
- 1 Combretum apiculatum (mohudiri)
- 2 Terminalia sericea (mogonono)
- 1 Lonchocarpus / Philenoptera (Mopororo)
- 1 Pterocarpus africanus (Mokwa)

Vegetation study for BW

- Dominant thorn species were identified as particularly relevant to the fire ecology in the study area as well as Botswana:
- **Invasive, burn well & also very common around homes in the study area**
 1. **Vachellia tortilis (umbrella thorn tree, “Mosu”) - formerly Acacia tortilis**
 2. Senegalia erubescens (Blue thorn, hookthorn “Moloto”)
 3. Senegalia mellifera (Black thorn, “Mongana”)

Vegetation study for BW

Based on building material Survey (325 samples):

- Only 89 structures (27.4%) were free of surrounding vegetation.
- The remaining 236 structures (72.6%) had vegetation at varying distances and intensities, and it was mostly **Vachellia tortilis**.

These findings underscore the importance of investigating the potential fire impacts of diverse vegetation types on built structures.

Vegetation study for BW

Vachellia Tortillis

Vegetation study for BW

**Senegalia
Erubescens**

Vegetation study for BW

**Senegalia
Mellifera**

Vegetation study for BW

Vegetation study for both SA and BW

Future work

- Mapping the distribution of these tree species using remote sensing and GIS in SA and BW.
- Conducting cone calorimeter tests.
- Conducting large scale experiments to characterize firebrands.

Vegetation study for both SA and BW

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Africa-Japan
Collaborative
Research

Long Term Africa-Japan Research and Innovation Partnership

Fire safe African homes on the wildland urban interface (AfriWUIFire)

Regulation in Africa: Case of Botswana and South Africa

Dr Phetole Ramatsoma, PDoc Fellow, Faculty of Economic and Management Sciences, Sol Plaatje University

(Presented by: Dr Doug Harebottle, CGC Director)

Institute of
SCIENCE TOKYO

Workshop 2 – 20 February 2025

www.spu.ac.za

Centre for Global Change

Programme of the NRF and DSI (Global Change Research Programme). Funding from DSI. Five HEIs in SA.

SPU-CGC - launched 1 September 2021

Conduct applied research in global and climate change research that has societal impact

Funding for PG bursaries, research costs and operation costs

AfriWUIFire - Project rationale

Wildland Urban Interface (WUI) fires cause multiple fatalities, injuries, displaced people, property losses and health- and environmental- issues.
How can we make our communities more resilient to these disasters?

This project seeks **to improve the resilience of African communities located in WUI areas by focusing on the study of firebrands and its impact on property loss.** Knowledge gained by research conducted in Japan will be applied in communities in South Africa. Experimental work previously developed will be replicated taking into account the African context.

AfriWUIFire - aims and objectives

- The aim of this research project is **to improve fire resilience of homes and structures in communities located in wildland urban interface (WUI) areas in Southern Africa**. This will be done by focusing on the impact of firebrands in property loss. To achieve this goal the objectives of this research are to:
 1. Characterize typical structures in South Africa and Botswana, including construction materials and construction typologies.
 2. Identify typical vegetation in South Africa and Botswana.
 3. Develop fire experiments to understand the impact of firebrands on different construction features. Experiments will be conducted in Japan and South Africa. An extensive database of full-scale fire experiments from Japan will be used as a basis.
 4. **Provide scientifically based inputs to develop guidelines for improving fire resilience in communities located in WUI areas.**
 5. **Look into policy and intervention in order to improve our response, policy, organisations, and codes.**
 6. Engage with local and international partners.

Problem statement

- There is a need for the prevention of damage to houses, property, livelihoods and loss of lives
- Evacuation warning models, and policies on cedars and fires (*Mutch et al 2011*)
- Generally poor implementation of policies that could assist in effective planning, particularly in high-risk areas (*Taccaliti et al 2023*)
- Globally, inadequacy and inequalities in socio-economic conditions → lack of preparedness in implementation of policies during disasters (*Orru et al. 2022*)
- In SA, Disaster Management Units lack systems to improve response strategies in fire-related emergencies (*Mamabola & Sebola 2021*)

Codes and guidelines: South Africa

South Africa – National Framework

- **Constitution (1996, Ch 2)**
 - Rights of citizens to good health and an environment that is harmless
- **Disaster Management Act 2002**
 - Government agencies deploy integrated resources, mitigate and assist in post-recovery (Ch 1)
 - Establishment of National Disaster Management Centre
 ☐ Provincial level (Ch 2)
 - Production of Disaster Management Plans (ensure preventive measures are in place, and assist vulnerable communities, evacuation plans) (Ch 3)
 - These processes strengthen public policy on disaster prevention and management (*Dookie and Spence-Hemmings 2022*)

<https://www.sanbi.org.za>

Codes and guidelines: South Africa

Fire Services Act 1987

- Section 1 – Fire brigade board at local levels (fire service responders must protect lives and property)
- Penney et al (2024) – urban and landscape design, types of construction and vegetation prohibit their performance
- Section 10 – Local authorities or controlling agencies to conduct regular risk assessments and fire planning
- Section 15 – Evacuation plans must be in place
- Beresford (2013) – Policy makers responsibility to ensure building codes are well articulated for fire risks
- Fire services related legislative framework important to bring WUI communities together for risk reduction (Kapalo et al 20121)

Codes and guidelines: South Africa

National Veld and Forest Fire Act 101 of 1998 (Department of Forestry, Fisheries and Environment)

- Aligns with Fire Brigade Services Act 1987
- To prevent and respond to forest, grassland, veld and mountainous fires (Ch1)
- Creation of firebreaks and removal of flammable material (owners) (Ch 4)
- Fire danger warnings
- Supports the development of the Fire Protection Association (FPA) structures (<https://www.pafpa.org/>)
- FPAs – assessing veldfire risks, climate conditions; develop veld fire management strategies, rules for members, train members and communities in fire-fighting and report to minister on statistics of veldfires
- FPAs should work with municipalities who owners of state land and should be a member (Ch 2)

Codes and guidelines: South Africa

- **State of Emergency Act 1997**
 - Makes available funding and resources in extreme cases
- **Public Finance Management Act 1999**
 - Disaster management, firefighting services, veld fires, emergency response regulations, codes, frameworks and policies all require financial resources for implementation
 - Local authorities → budgetary plans for emergency response and risk management
 - The Act makes allowance for budgetary and financial plans to be controlled through its policies and provides guidelines for organs of state for managing and accounting for funds in disaster situations

Codes and guidelines: South Africa

- **National Building Regulations and Building Standards Act 103 of 1977**

Provides for:

- **the promotion of uniformity in the law relating to the erection of buildings in the areas of jurisdiction of local authorities;**
- **the prescribing of building standards;**
- *Section 16. (1) The Minister, after consultation with. the Administrator of a province, including the Territory, in which the area of jurisdiction of a local authority is situated, may order such local authority to report to him on - a) the adequacy of measures in or in connection with buildings in its area of jurisdiction **against fire, floods or other disasters and to make recommendations in order to remove any inadequacies in such measures;***
- BUT no specific WUI considerations!

Codes and guidelines: Botswana

Botswana – Policy Framework

Constitution (1966, Ch. 1)

- Section 4: lives of people should be protected and those of their properties
- Section 17: provision for declaration in case of emergency (President duty)

Botswana Land Policy (2015)

- 50-85% of woodlands, forests and savanna in Botswana, Angola, Zambia, Zimbabwe (*Heikkliä 2007*). Localised alien woody species. Wildfires are common.
- Consultation led to two state land administration system: Statutory and Customary (tribal)
- State Land Act (CAP 32:01) and Tribal Land Act (CAP 32:02)
- Policy – developed in response to poor agricultural potential but good wildlife, veld products, minerals and forests. Socio-economic outcome. Migration of people to urban centers – economic needs (increase in urban plots)
- Government responsibility to provide clearance for land planning based on landscaping for building design and materials (*Beresford 2023*)

<https://www.info-botswana.com/>

Codes and guidelines: Botswana

Building Control Act (65:02)

The Minister may, by statutory instrument, make regulations for regulating all or any of the following matters:

- *the construction of buildings, and the materials to be used in the construction of buildings;*
- *the lighting and ventilation of buildings, and the dimensions of rooms intended for human habitation; the height of buildings*
- *the height of chimneys, not being separate buildings, above the roof of the buildings of which they form part;*
- *(e) the drainage of buildings, including the means for conveying refuse water and water from roofs and from yards appurtenant to buildings; cesspools and other means for the reception or disposal of foul matter in connection with buildings;*
- *(f) ashpits in connection with buildings; wells, tanks and cisterns for the supply of water for human consumption in connection with buildings; stoves and other fittings in buildings (not being electric stoves or fittings), in so far as regulations with respect to such matters are required **for the prevention of fire**; and private sewers; communications between drains and sewers and between sewers.*

Summary conceptual framework

Credit: P. Ramatsoma

Conclusion

a. Existing policy and guidelines

- Not a large focus on WUI components (?)
- Most government struggling to share information and communicate policies on how to prevent and combat WUI – community engagement important

b. Role of climate change

- Increase in climate variability → changes to vegetation structure and composition
- Government response → policy perspective

c. AfriWUIFire

- Provide additional information for further development and improvement of policies, guidelines and codes to reduce damage, improve response, and clearly outline role and responsibilities of authorities and land-owners.
- Need for policy and codes workshop?

Thank you

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Africa-Japan
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Research

Long Term Africa-Japan Research and Innovation Partnership

Long Term Africa-Japan Research and Innovation Partnership

Progress to Develop Global Test Methods for Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fires

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We Cannot Look to Future Ignoring Past

Wildland-Urban Interface Fires

Develop Resilient Communities of the Future

Why WUI Fires Present Unique Challenges?

WUI Fire Science Remains Elusive

Great Meireki Fire – Before USA Existed

- Meireki Fire (1657)
 - 60% of urban area burnt
 - Castle tower burnt -> never reconstructed

Meireki Fire (1657) Wikipedia

Great Chicago Fire of 1871

Currier and Ives, Chicago Historical Society

Modern Times

- Wildfires that spread into communities, known as **wildland-urban interface (WUI) fires** have destroyed communities throughout the world
- Large outdoor fires that pose risk to built environment are **urban fires**
- **Informal settlement fires**, common in the developing world, are another important example

Fuel 314 (2022) 122805

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](#)

Fuel

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/fuel

ELSEVIER

Letter to the editor

The importance of combustion science to unravel complex processes for informal settlement fires, urban fires, and wildland-urban interface (WUI) fires

Check for updates

A B S T R A C T

Devastating large outdoor fires have been responsible for destruction of vast amounts of infrastructure and loss of human life. At first glance, the complex ignition, fire spread processes, and degree of gaseous and particulate emissions appear daunting during these large-scale destructive events. As part of this perspective paper, fundamental combustion science is discussed as a critical need to unravel these complex physical processes observed in large outdoor fires. An important aspect is that many of the detailed physics of these processes have yet to be fully revealed. In turn, this is a major barrier to developing computational methods to be able to predict and understand how large outdoor fires spread. The range of topics discussed is intentionally not comprehensive but intended to serve as an introductory list to engage the combustion community in this important, pressing research area.

S.L. Manzello and S. Suzuki, *Fuel* 2022

Flame Spread Processes Similar

Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fires

Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fires

Wildland-Urban Interface, Fig. 1 Examples of interface WUI in (a) Fort McMurray, Alberta, Canada (Canadian Forest Service/Wiens B.); (b) Sydney, Australia

(CSIRO/McArthur N.); (c) Australia (Google Maps); and (d) Slave Lake, Alberta, Canada (University of Alberta/Flannigan M.)

Wildland-Urban Interface, Fig. 4 Number of WUI mapping studies across the world, summarized by country (non-exhaustive numbers)

Johnston, L., Bianchi, R., Jappiot, M. (2019). Wildland-Urban Interface. In: Manzello, S.L. (eds) Encyclopedia of Wildfires and Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fires. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-51727-8_130-1

African Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fires

- WUI fires have become a **significant problem in Southern Africa as well**
- **Firebrand Attack is key issue**

Analysis of fire spread mechanism
in 2017 Knysna fires

WUI fire in Cape Town 2021
Mike Hutchings/Reuters

Fire Safe African Homes on the Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI)

- Botswana
- South Africa

Need to engage other African countries

WUI fire disasters possible in many other countries

Africa-Japan
Collaborative
Research

WUI Fires Global Problem

Only a Matter of Time For Huge WUI Fire in Your Country?

WUI Fires in Hawaii

Maui 2023

Hawaii
No WUI standards and
codes at all!

Maui fires in pics: Aerial photos show extent of destruction caused by Hawaii wildfires | The Independent

Homes and buildings on the waterfront in Lahaina burned to the ground (*AFP via Getty Images*)

WUI Fires in LA

January 2025

**Massive
Destruction
Observed**

**USA WUI
Standards
No Firebrand Shower
Test Methods!**

The wind whips embers as the
Palisades Fire burns during a
windstorm on the west side of Los
Angeles, January 7.
REUTERS/Ringo Chiu

Largest U.S. Fire Loss Incidents (NFPA)

<u>Incident</u>	<u>Date</u>	<u>Adjusted Loss (2018 dollars)</u>
1. World Trade Center, NY	2001	\$47.4 billion
<u>2. Northern California WUI Fire (2017), CA</u>	<u>2017</u>	<u>\$10.2 billion</u>
3. San Francisco, CA Earthquake, CA	1906	\$9.7 billion
<u>4. The Camp WUI Fire, CA</u>	<u>2018</u>	<u>\$8.5 billion</u>
5. Great Chicago Fire, IL	1871	\$3.5 billion
<u>6. The Woolsey WUI Fire, CA</u>	<u>2018</u>	<u>\$2.9 billion</u>
<u>7. Oakland WUI fire, CA</u>	<u>1991</u>	<u>\$2.8 billion</u>
<u>8. Southern California Fire Storm, CA</u>	<u>2007</u>	<u>\$2.1 billion</u>
<u>9. Southern California WUI Fire , CA</u>	<u>2017</u>	<u>\$1.8 billion</u>
<u>10. The Valley Fire, CA</u>	<u>2015</u>	<u>\$1.6 billion</u>
11. Great Boston Fire, MA	1872	\$1.6 billion
12. Polyolefin Plant, TX	2000	\$1.5 billion
<u>13. Cerro Grande WUI Fire, NM</u>	<u>2000</u>	<u>\$1.5 billion</u>
<u>14. Cedar WUI Fire, CA</u>	<u>2003</u>	<u>\$1.4 billion</u>
15. Baltimore Conflagration, MD	1904	\$1.4 billion

9 of the top 15 are WUI Fires – Hawaii, LA not included!

Develop Resilient Communities of the Future

Develop Resilient Communities

2015 ASTM E05 (Fire Standards) sponsored a workshop to study wildland-urban interface (WUI) fire standards and codes issues

Office of the State Fire Marshal of California embarked on a course to develop standard test methods and building codes for WUI communities, in a similar manner to the development of such methods for urban fires

Current WUI fire standards and codes are reflection of current (or lack thereof) science

2017 Due to interest from ASTM International activity, as well as increase of WUI fires globally, ISO TC92 Fire Safety, and the International Association for Fire Safety Science (IAFSS), sponsored two workshops to look at the WUI fire problem in a more global manner

THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION
FOR FIRE SAFETY SCIENCE

International FORUM of Fire Research Directors Research Needs to Address Growing WUI Fire Dilemma

The Growing Global
Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fire Dilemma:
Priority Needs for Research

S.L. Manzello et al., Fire Safety Journal, 2018

Research into WUI fires *lags* other areas of fire safety science research

Fire safety science community **focused on fires inside buildings several decades**

Develop Resilient Communities

ISO TC92 TG03 was setup with the intent to propose a path forward for the topic Large Outdoor Fires and the Built Environment for ISO TC92

Share
Progress

Led to the establishment of ISO TC 92/WG14

Led to establishment of IAFSS LOF&BE

LOF&BE focuses on tackling large outdoor fire challenges like wildland fires, WUI fires, informal settlement fires, and urban fires

Includes subgroups: Ignition Resistant Communities (IRC), Emergency Management and Evacuation (EME), and Large Outdoor Fire Fighting (LOFF). LOFF has been replaced with a Fire Service Advisory Panel (FSAP)

THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION
FOR FIRE SAFETY SCIENCE

Large **O**utdoor **F**ires **&** **B**uilt **E**nvironment

Samuel L. Manzello, Sara McAllister & Sayaka Suzuki

ISO TC92/WG14 Team

France

Germany

Sweden

USA

China

Netherlands

Convener of ISO TC92/WG14

Samuel L. Manzello

Austria

Japan

Korea

United Kingdom

Trinidad and Tobago

Hungary

Greece

Canada

Australia

ISO TR 24188:2022

Global Overview of Different Approaches to Standardization

← ICS ← 13 ← 13.220 ← 13.220.01

ISO/TR 24188:2022

Large outdoor fires and the built environment — Global overview of different approaches to standardization

Abstract

[Preview](#)

This document provides a review of global testing methodologies related to the vulnerabilities of buildings from large outdoor fire exposures. It also provides information on land use management practices. Some of the test methods outlined in this document have been developed in the context of building fires and extrapolated to external fire exposures.

General information

Status : Published

Publication date : 2022-06

Edition : 1

Number of pages : 19

Technical Committee : ISO/TC 92 Fire safety

ICS : 13.220.01 Protection against fire in general

This standard contributes to the following Sustainable Development Goals:

9 **15**

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Format

Language

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English

Paper

English

CHF 118

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ISO TR 24188:2025

Global Overview of Different Approaches to Standardization

Updated definitions
and one figure

ISO/TR 24188:2025
Large outdoor fires and the built environment
— Global overview of different approaches
to standardization

Published (Edition 2, 2025)

Language: English
Format: PDF + ePub, Paper
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Abstract
This document provides a review of global testing methodologies related to the vulnerabilities of buildings from large outdoor fire exposures. It also provides information on land use management practices.

General information
Status : Published
Publication date : 2025-02
Stage : International Standard published [60.60]
Edition : 2
Number of pages : 18
Technical Committee : ISO/TC 92
ICS : 13.220.01
RSS updates

ISO TR 24188:2025

Tested structural element	Country	Method	Radiative effect scenario	Firebrands scenario	Wind effect scenario	Others
Roofs	Japan	ISO 12468-1	No	Cribs placed on roof surface, of different types according to a building protection zone criteria (FPZ, QFPZ, "Low-flame-spread")	Yes. The wind speed is set to 3.0 m/s.	—
	USA / Canada	CAN/ULC-S107 ^[10] ASTM E108 ^[17] UL 790 ^[11] NFPA 276 ^[12]	Flames from a calibrated burner	Burning standard brands, Intermittent /cyclic flame exposure test	Yes. The spread of flame test is conducted at a 5,4 m/s (12 mph) wind speed.	—
	France	CEN TS 1187 ^[34] (test 3)	Exposure to a radiant panel of (10-12,5) kW/m ² (includes slope angle effect of the roof) during 30 min	Standard cribs placed on roof surface	To some extent, using a blower; for fire propagation on roof only, not for hot gases.	—
	Australia	AS 1530.8.1 ^[9] AS 1530.8.2 ^[8]	4+1 scenarios: — Direct flame impingement, based on interior fire exposure. — 4 scenarios of distant flame impingement: radiant panel (or radiation produced from furnace) at exposures of (12,5, 19, 29 or 40) kW/m ² for 10 min.	Burning debris simulated by standard wood cribs placed beside the wall.	No	Specific to wildland fires exposure.

No country in entire world – firebrand shower test methods!

ISO TR 24188:2025

Tested structural element	Country	Method	Radiative effect scenario	Firebrands scenario	Wind effect scenario	Others
Exterior walls Facades	Japan	ISO 834-1 Fire resistance	Yes Based on interior fire exposure	No	No	Adapted for long-duration exposure scenarios.
		JIS A 1310 ^[26] Reaction to fire for facades	Main façade: 1,8 m × 4,1 m, wing façade (optional): 0,9 m × 4,1 m Opening in main façade: 0,9 m × 0,9 m Fire source: propane (approx. 900 kW), test duration: 20 min.	No	No	—
	USA / Canada	USA – ASTM E119 ^[2] or UL 263 ^[3] Canada – CAN/ULC- S101 ^[4]	Yes – USA – Fire resistance can be based on interior or exterior fire exposure. Yes – Canada – Fire resistance based on interior fire exposure only.	No	No	Internal fire aggression. Adapted for long- duration exposure scenarios.
	USA	SFM 12-7A-1 ^[6] ASTM E2707 ^[7]	Yes 10 min exposure to 150 kW fire, reflective of plants, trash, deck, etc. beside the wall.	—	—	External fire aggression. Adapted for short- duration exposure scenarios.
	France	ISO 834-1 EN 1363-2 ^[37]	General ignition-resistant material, internal fire. Based on interior fire exposure.	No	No	Adapted for long- duration exposure scenarios.
			General ignition-resistant material, external fire. Based on exterior fire exposure (reaching 660 °C after 30 min).	No	No	Adapted for long- duration exposure scenarios.
		Facades LEPIR2 ^[36]	A two-level facade, with fire starting in the lower compartment (fire of 600 kg of wood cribs), and openings at the two levels (no glass in the generic setup). A 30-min fire exposure is performed.	No	No	—
	Australia	AS 1530.8.1 ^[9] AS 1530.8.2 ^[8]	Similar to roofs.			

ISO TR 24188:2025

Tested structural element	Country	Method	Radiative effect scenario	Firebrands scenario	Wind effect scenario	Others
Vents	USA	ASTM E2886 ^[13]	No	Firebrand generator (fan)	No	Also contains flame intrusion test using different test procedures.
Decks	USA	SFM 12-7A-4 ^[14] ASTM E2632 ^[15] ASTM E2726 ^[16]	Flame of 80 kW for 3 min, for 2 scenarios of deck ignited by firebrands accumulation: under or over the deck.	Standard burning brand placed over the deck, with a fan blowing an airflow of approximately 5,4 m/s (12 mph) over the specimen for 40 min.	Yes, in ASTM E2726 / SFM 12-7A-4 No, in ASTM E2632	Adapted for short-duration exposure scenarios.
Eaves Eaves and soffits	USA / Canada	SFM 12-7A-3 ^[18] ASTM E2957 ^[19] CAN/ULC-S114 ^[22] , CAN/ULC-S135 ^[23]	Flame of 300 kW for 10 min. Regulated based on combustibility of materials.	No No	No No	Adapted for short-duration exposure scenarios.
Windows	USA	SFM 12-7A-2 ^[20]	150 kW, 100 mm × 1 000 mm diffusion burner under the target window. The specimen is exposed to the flame for 8 min.	No	No	—
	Australia	AS 1530.8.1 ^[9] AS 1530.8.2 ^[8]	Similar to exterior walls.			
Other provisions – reaction-to-fire	USA	SFM 12-7A-5 ^[21]	2 burners of 88 kW for 10 min.	No	No	Ignition-resistant material. Steiner Tunnel test method ASTM E84. ^[49]
	France	EN 13501-1 ^[39] M-Classification	Similar to requirements for enclosures.	No	No	—

No country in entire world – firebrand shower test methods!

ISO Standard Firebrand Generator (ISO 6021:2024)

Published International Standard March, 2024

Fire Safety Journal 91 (2017) 784–790

ELSEVIER

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Fire Safety Journal

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/firesaf

IAFSS 12th Symposium 2017

Experiments to provide the scientific-basis for laboratory standard test methods for firebrand exposure

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	International Standard
Firebrand generator	ISO 6021 First edition 2024-03

Advancements in Combustion

ISO Firebrand Generator

SWIPE →

"In March 2024, the ISO Technical Committee (TC) 92 Fire Safety, published ISO 6021:2024 – Firebrand generator. The ISO firebrand generator is based on the firebrand generator developed by CI members Samuel L. Manzello (Tohoku University, Japan and Reax Engineering, USA) and Sayaka Suzuki (Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan)."

SWIPE →

The ISO firebrand generator, installed in a wind facility, is being used to study how firebrand showers interact with an obstacle (0.6 m high by 1.2 m wide) placed downstream. The applied wind speed is 6 m/s.

SWIPE →

The ISO firebrand generator, installed in a wind facility, is being used to study the ignition of a Noble-fir tree (1.2 m high). The applied wind speed is 3 m/s.

ISO 2024

Standardized Post-Fire Data Collection

[Standards](#) [Sectors](#) [About ISO](#) [News](#) [Taking part](#) [Store](#)

[← TC ← ISO/TC 92](#)

ISO/AWI 24944

Standardized Post-Fire Data Collection Methods from Large Outdoor Fires

Under development

A working group has prepared a draft.

Abstract

Post-fire data collection for large outdoor fires will be reviewed based on available studies conducted for wildland-urban interface fires, urban fires, including post-earthquake urban fires, and informal settlement fires. These studies will be used to develop a standardized data collection methodology for large outdoor fires that may be used in the event of future large outdoor fire disasters. A standardized approach, at the international level, will be required to be able to assess and compare fire spread and damage across all these large outdoor fire types.

General information

Status : Under development
Stage : New project registered in TC/SC work programme
[20.00]

Edition : 1

Technical Committee : [ISO/TC 92](#)

 [RSS updates](#)

Harmonizing Methods for Thermal Flux Exposure

← TC ← ISO/TC 92

ISO/AWI TS 25399

Large Outdoor Fires and the Built Environment:
harmonizing the test methods for thermal
flux exposure

Under development

A working group has prepared a draft.

Abstract

This TS first presents a review of the different worldwide existing tests to assess the resistance of building components (mainly vents and roofs) under the thermal flux exposure during a large outdoor fire. Then a methodology is proposed to harmonize these tests into a single international ISO standard.

General information

Status : Under development

Stage : New project registered in TC/SC work programme
[20.00]

Edition : 1

Technical Committee : ISO/TC 92

 [RSS updates](#)

Why WUI Fires Present Unique Challenges?

Lack of Resources for Accepted Knowledge

Book Printed July 2020

Also a Living Edition!

171 contributions published

More than 200 authors from all over the world

<https://link.springer.com/referencework/10.1007/978-3-319-51727-8>

SPRINGER NATURE

WUI Fire Science Remains Elusive

- The complex ignition, fire spread processes, and degree of gaseous and particulate emissions **appear daunting** during WUI fire events
- Some needed studies relevant to WUI fire processes:
 - **Firebrand combustion processes**
 - Gaseous and particulate emissions
 - Transition from smoldering combustion to flaming combustion
 - Initial ignition of vegetative and structural fuels, subsequent flame spread
 - Fire whirl combustion processes

Detailed chemistry and physics of these processes have yet to be fully revealed

Barrier to develop computational methods to predict/understand WUI fires

Structure Ignition Mechanisms in WUI Fires

Direct Flame Contact

Thermal Radiation

Firebrands

Challenge: Wide Range of Scales

900 km (domain)

~8 km (grid cell)

1 km (domain)

~1 m (grid cell)

Regional

Landscape

Community

Fuel elements

Combustion Community Critical

**W. Mell, S.L. Manzello, et al.,
Int. J. Wildland Fire, 2010**

Firebrand Processes in WUI Fires

Firebrand Generation from Vegetation Combustion

- Pyrolysis of fuel elements is an important mechanism
- During vegetative combustion process, wind flow around fuel elements generates and imposes aerodynamic forces
- These forces produce moments and stresses along fuel elements while pyrolysis simultaneously thermally degrades them and reduces their structural integrity
- Firebrands are formed when a critical point is reached

Conifer Tree Combustion
Manzello *et al.*,
Int. J. Wildland Fire, 2007

B. Barr and D.K. Ezekoye
Proc. Comb. Inst., 2013

Ezekoye, O.A., Wessies, S.S. (2018). Vegetative Firebrand Attack. In: Manzello, S.L. (eds) Encyclopedia of Wildfires and Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) Fires. Springer, Cham.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-51727-8_66-1

Summary

- New thinking needed to address global WUI fire problem
 - **African and Japanese Combustion and Engineering Communities**
 - **WUI fires are a serious threat and should not be underestimated**
- WUI fires need global cooperation
 - To quantify firebrand production from vegetation combustion, a uniform test method that may be used in any country is needed
- **WUI fire problem too complex to continue down current path**

Special Issue in Applications in Energy and Combustion Science

Applications in Energy and Combustion Science

Open access

Wildland Fires and Wildland-Urban interface (WUI) Fires

Submission deadline: 30 September 2025

Wildland fires that spread into urban areas, known as wildland-urban interface (WUI) fires, have become a complex and challenging task for governments around the world. Recent WUI fires have resulted in the complete destruction of entire communities. WUI fires are distinct from wildland fires, as WUI fires contain the combustion of human-made fuels, in addition to vegetative fuels present in wildland fires. Such complex fuels, and different time scales involved, render understanding and predicting fire spread through WUI communities as major scientific complexity. Both wildland fires and WUI fires have not received significant attention from the combustion community. It is surprising since both fire types have relevant chemical and physical processes that the combustion community has the skills and tools needed to make headways in scientific understanding sorely needed by stakeholders across the globe. As part of this special issue in Applications in Energy and Combustion Science (AECS), papers of interest include, but are not limited, to the following topics:

- Characterizing particulate formation from vegetative and human-made fuels in WUI fires
- Firebrand combustion processes in wildland fires and WUI fires
- Smoldering combustion processes for vegetative and human-made fuels in WUI fires
- The transition from smoldering combustion to flaming combustion in WUI fires
- The interaction between flames from vegetative fuel to building elements in WUI fires
- Mitigation strategies on the combustion of building elements in WUI fires, including fire retardant effects on combustion
- Simulation studies of large-scale wildland fires and WUI fires, including detailed combustion modelling
- Pyrolysis of live and dead ornamental fuels in the WUI
- Emissions from wildland fires and WUI fires

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